

Transformation of Buddhism in Koguryo Kingdom of Korea

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Abstract:

The ancestors of the Korean people settled and put down the deep roots of their culture in to the southern part of China. Now known Manchuria and into the Peninsula now known as Korea.¹ A first like most ancient people fear ruled their lives and they needed to “tame” nature and overcome natural disaster in order to survive. Therefore like most primitive people they believe in Taoism. Throughout its long history Korean Buddhism has always been concerned with issues of syncretism. On one Level this syncretism tendency has involved interchange with other philosophical and spiritual system in particular Confucianism. Taoism and the indigenous Korean Shamanism .On the other level the syncretism process has been internal involving and reconciliation of conflicting School of Buddhist thought in an effort to create a single harmonious whole. Borrowing the terminology traditional to Korean Buddhist itself ,we can say that the history of Korean Buddhism itself has been focused on the efforts to create an all inclusive Buddhist Doctrine or t'ong pulgyo(Buddhism of total interpretation).¹ In this paper I will discuss Development and transformation of Buddhism in kogurya which was a kingdom of Korea.

Key words: Buddhism, Transformation, Spiritual, Worshipped

¹ Takeuchi yoshinari, Buddhist spirituality ,Vol II ,p 56

Before Buddhism entered in to Korean, Korean people come to believe that all natural phenomena are god or there incarnation. They believe in the power of natural phenomena such as the blue sky, cloud, wind, rain, Snow Mountain, sea, river, trees and rocks. Consequently all natural disasters such as drought, floods, thunderstorm and the contagious disease were considered as sign of anger of the God and so their punishment. Korean people tried to please The God. Pleasing the Gods formed the foundation for the religious activities and become a very important part of life and beliefs of Korean people of day gone by.² Among the religious event the most important one was Chech – on-Daehoe.. The sky and all the natural phenomena were worshiped.Yonggo of Puyo,Tongmeang of Cholbonbuyo and Muchon of Tong-yae are all example of this primitive from the religion of worship of the natural Gods were common at the time of the three Kingdom koguruya,Peckche & Shilla. Its primitiveness lay in its lack of organization is unsystematic approach to believe.³

The Miracle of Korean is that in spite of interminable internal strike and foreign interference. Its people have maintained a strong national and ethical identity and contributed significantly beauty and distinctive human history. This contribution is now where more evident site generally hostile relations with both China and Japan, Korea acted as an important intermediary in the spread of Buddhism from China to Japan and developed it on distinction from Buddhism throw intimate through often unwanted contact with its two powerful neighbors.⁴Surrounding by China to the west, Japan to the East and Manchuria to the north. It is surprising that Korea emerged with such a distinctive historical ethnic and cultural identity and yet Korea's route extent deep in the history. The Korean Peninsula was inhabited by at least the fourth Millennium BCE. The use of bronze in Korea begin late in the second Millennium BCE and the local production of iron has begun by about 300 BCE a technology imported by the refugees from the turmoil of the warring states period of China 453-221 BCE. From this period Chinese influence in Korea grow steadily through migration military conflict and the diplomatic contacts.⁵ It was in this environment that Buddhism a highly sophisticated religion

² The history and culture of Buddhism in Korea ,The Korean Buddhist research institute ,p37

³ Ibid

⁴ .Noble Ross Reat, religion of the world Buddhism A History,p-166

⁵ Ibid p 167

was introduced to Korea by land or by sea. Though foreign to the Korean people at the beginning, Buddhism is intrinsically tolerant and the adopted character enabled a smooth acceptance in their environment.⁶ Historically Buddhism has always been based on the principles of harmony and the agreement and it was this quality which created the necessary circumstances for Buddhism to cease being a foreign teaching and become truly Korean. Later on Buddhism served not only as a religion but also as a culture philosophy and spiritual pivot point around which to sublimate all the joys and sorrow of life. The original beliefs held by the Korean people were adjusted are greatly change with the introduction of Buddhism. Some of these adjustment consisted is an evolution of the traditional God in to a new ones. As believe change along the above patterns everything came to be included in the scope of Buddhism. This remains one of overall difference between Buddhism and other invaded religion.⁷ Buddhism never appears or shows itself to be arrogant. It is always intrinsically open minded, offering the people education and inspiring them with its deep understanding of life. Buddhism Never goes in extreme like that neither denies the God nor encourage the worshiped of God. It always follows middle path. It even as enlightenment the true and emancipation of the human condition, all the while taking in the consideration the change in time circumstances and public feeling. Buddhism is always humans and centered and realistic in its approach of life.

One of another is special characteristic of Buddhism was that to observed every aspect of the indigenous thinking of the people even though Idea and the customs which were not in harmony with reality. This allowed the people to learn for the themselves and adjust these thoughts and customs as it became necessary and their development. This is the intrinsic art of Buddhism right from the time of Buddha to the present day. Buddhism harmonized and educate the people according to the time and peace and their personal need.⁸ In the second century BCE the Han dynasty of China move to subjugate the tribal people to the north east of Chinese heartland including those of Korean Peninsula. By forming alliance and the confederations these various tribal peoples including

⁶ Ibid,p167

⁷ Takeuchi yoshanari, Buddhist spirituality ,Vol II ,p 57

⁸ .Noble Ross Reat,religion of the world Buddhism A History,p-166

Mongols, Manchurians and the Koreans periodically threatened the security and the integrity of Imperial China particularly in border areas. Chinese initiatives to the subjugate these barbarians were largely successful by the second century BCE. This resulted in the establishment of Korean peninsula of four Chinese administrative divisions commonly known as the commentaries which governed the Peninsula.⁹Up to 7th century BCE the Korean Peninsula was divided in the three separate kingdoms. Koguryo(37 BCE – 668 CE), Paekche(18 BCE-660CE and Silla (57 BCE – 668 CE). These three Buddhism Took hold in the Koguryo first. Introduced by Chinese monk late in the 4th century it was quickly adopted by the country's autocracy receiving extensive Government support.¹⁰ Kogoryu's ruling class was attracted to Buddhism in part because of the supernatural power attributes to it, as a means of the strengthening the Kingdom against attack the strength of neighboring China being considered a prime illustration of its magical efficacy but Buddhism also offers Koguryo nobility and entire system of the advance culture bringing with its exalted philosophical vision of reality as well as magnificent art, architecture, music and literature.¹¹ By this time to other powerful religious philosophical system had already enter the Korean Peninsula from China. The first of these Confucianism was two closely associated with Chinese style bureaucratic examination system to appeal to the aristocratic governments of the Korean Kingdom all three of which determine leadership through family lineage.¹² The second Taoism was more successful. A religion emphasizing quiescence magic inner alchemy and a naturalistic philosophy its pantheon of spirits and god were soon grafted on to the archaic religious complex of Korean shamanism forming what may be termed a shamanistic Taoism for a period this hybrid creation overshadowed both Buddhism and the Confucianism on the Peninsula becoming the basic religion of the people especially the common folk of the countryside. The introduction of Buddhism into the Korea must

⁹ Noble Ross Reat,religion of the world Buddhism A History,p-165

¹⁰ .Buswell Robert E,jr.Cha'n Hermeneutics :A Korean view, In Buddhist ,p 231-56

¹¹ Park sung Bae,Buddhist faith and sudden enlightenment,Albay:p 108

¹² Lancaster Lewis R.and Sung bae park,eds,the Korean Buddhist cannon: A descriptive catalogue

therefore ultimately be understood in the context of its synergetic harmonization with the shamanistic Taoism already present in three Kingdoms to early Korea.¹³ Buddhism was introduced to the three Kingdoms of Koguryo, Peckche, and Shilla harmonizing with the indigenous beliefs. Buddhism gave thought, Culture and the religion to the Korean people starting with the royal court and spreading down through the people. From the time of the introduction of Buddhism Korean culture began to develop many Buddhist monks went to China to study and they in turn influenced many of Chinese scholars of their day. The Koguryo kingdom in the Northern part of the Peninsula existed until the unification of Peninsula in 668 CE. Let us now take a look the transmission of Buddhism to Kingdom and its substance development then we will look at the activities of Buddhism at that time as well as the work carried out by Koguryo Buddhism in foreign countries.¹⁴

According to the Korean history Buddhism is generally considered to have been initially introduced in 372 CE the second year of the reign of the Koguryo King Sosurim (371-384 CE) Chinese king Fuchien of the former Ch'in sent statue of Buddha along with a text by the monk envoy master Sundo (Chinese Shuntao) to the Koguryo king Sosurim at 372 CE. Grateful for the gift, King Sosurim thanked the Chinese king by sending the special envoys in return. Two years later in 374 master Ado came to the Koguryo. Then in 375 King Sosurim built Songmuh-Sa (Ch'omun-sa) for master Sundo and Iburan for the master Ado. This was the beginning of Korean Buddhism. In spite of the seeming unanimity of scholars concerning the introduction of Buddhism in Koguryo. The Chinese Monk Chih-Tao-Lin (374-366) from Eastern Ch'in sent a letter to the Koguryo monk. The name of the Korean monk is not known. The contents of the letter is written in Liang Kaoseng Chuan. This information would place in the introduction of Buddhism to Korea about 50 or 60 years prior of the official date of 372. Liang biographies of the eminent monks we are told that Buddhism was introduced to Koguryo in 396. In this record we are told that Chinese master Tanshi brought many sutras and the Vinaya to Liaotung in Koguryo. In the late fourth century he taught the three vehicles Hinayana Mahayana and

¹³ Lancaster Lewis R. Son Kikun and Yu Chai Shin ed. Buddhism in Koryo: A royal religion. Berkeley: Institute of East Asian Studies 1996.

¹⁴ Noble Ross Reat, Religion of the World Buddhism A History, p-166

vajrayana and the Trisharna the three refuses Buddha Dharma and Sangha and the Panchshila the five precepts. This is called the beginning of Buddhism in Korea. Master Tanshi returned to China at the beginning of reign of the Chinese King each Yi-Xi(405-418). This Monk was called introduction of Buddhism in seems confusing. Master Tanshi brought to pure Chinese .budhism to master Tao-an(312-385)to Koguryo. Tanshi not only introduced Buddhism to Koguryo but he also did an extraordinary meritorious service in reconstructed Chinese Buddhism which has been oppressed by king Tai-wu-di from northern wei from 446 until 451.¹⁵

Buddhism introduce to Koguryo in the reign of Sosurim, temples were built and the Buddhism became widespread. Unfortunately we don't have proper information about any other activities of the two monk who introduced Buddhism. We have no information concerning the response and reaction to Buddhism by the people of Koguryo and the method used to spread and popularized Buddhism is a foreign religion. In 391 Sosurim gave an order that "Buddhism should be worshiped and believed so that people can get good fortune. "We can clearly see that a believer in Buddhism was encouraged nationally. The king commanded his people to believe in Buddhism showing that he played an important part in the education of the people. Secondly Buddhism was understood as a teaching which give good fortune The king did not just order the people to merely worship and believe in Buddhism but he recommended Buddhism because it would bring good fortune Thirdly the concept of Buddhism believe in encompassed trust and confidence. Though believe the king felt that the people would be able to rightly understood the practice Buddhism and then obtain benefit. Buddhism teaching of truth we cannot expect good fortune without sincere believe. In 392 King Kowang-gaet'o build nine temples in P;yong yang. These nine temples are placed where people cultivate good fortune and overcome bad karma .The 21st century king Munja(419-519)build Kuganga-sa in 498. These are no precise detail but scholars things that the temple must have been built in Ch'ongam near lake teadong and P'yong yang a side that was excavated in 1938.¹⁶

¹⁵ ibid

¹⁶ The history and culture of Buddhism in Korea ,The Korean Buddhist research institute ,p38

In 576 a minister Wanggodok sent master Uiyon to norther Chou to learn the origin of Buddhism and to study Chinese Buddhism. From Fashang, master Uiyon brought back were some shastra including dushabhumi, pragyaparmita and vajraketika .Prajanaparmita giving some idea of material study at that time Though the record to know about Koguryo Buddhism are few and limited but many Koguryo Monk contributed and developed Buddhism even beyond Koguryo boundaries. Koguryo Buddhism expanded very rapidly with the help of the Kings. These were a crisis when Taoism spreading. A historical record said that the King Pojang the next the last Koguryo king accepted Taoism from general Kaesomun and had Buddhist temples changed in to Taoist temple in 643.¹⁷

There are so many Koguryo monks who went abroad for the Dharma and many of them became famous for their teachings in other countries. Koguryo monks went to China to study sutras for there was the source of Buddhism for Koguryo. Most of the monks at that time wanted to study in China and they considered it great honour to able to so. Master Hyep'yon, master Srundnang, master Hyegwan, master Temjing, many Koguryo monk contributed to the culture and growth of Buddhism in Japan. So that Koguryo Buddhism flourished. Pojang the next the last Koguryo king accepted Taoism from general Kaesomun and had Buddhist temples changed in to Taoist temple in 643.

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